

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LETHAPA****FIRST NAME: MOTLHAKENG****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2013 on Windows 10 PRO)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
2. First-Person Singular versus Academic Style (EUCLID 2019, 16)
3. Literature Review (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)
5. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)

DE-MISTIFYING ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Until a week ago, I was skeptical about learning academic writing. I was cynical when asked to take the English language test as part of my application because I believed it was my second language that I learned throughout my entire academic life. It does not mean that I was confident with my writing skills; instead, I thought I could improve it by writing more and more and not necessarily learning about writing. However, as I started interacting with reading materials for period one, I found myself scratching my head one too many times. The knowledge gap became more apparent, and I realized the value of academic writing at a doctoral and international level. In this paper, I will argue that learning academic writing is essential, and I will also discuss the misconceptions I had in the five concepts. The five concepts' which I chose from the coursepack are (1) plagiarism, (2) personal versus academic writing, (3) literature review, (4) style guide, and (5) Latin abbreviations and expressions.

2) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is not a new concept for anyone who has passed through both undergraduate and graduate studies. The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

defines plagiarism as “using other peoples’ work and ideas without giving proper credit to the original source thus violating the rights of the original author to their intellectual outputs” (All European Academies 2017, 8). The words “proper credit” may denote that one can give credit but not correctly. Plagiarism can be a tricky endeavor because while the solution to avoiding plagiarism is to properly cite the author or source of information (EUCLID 2019, 6), it must adhere to a proper referencing style. A citation may be correct; however, if it is not according to the institutions’ referencing style, it can be regarded as wrong! For example, the sample quote provided in the coursepack on page six omitted the year of publication in the in-text citation. This type of plagiarism is the one that Maurer, Kappe, and Zaka refer to as: “accidental plagiarism: which is due to lack of plagiarism knowledge, and understanding of referencing style being practiced at an institute” (1990, 1051). Therefore, one needs to acquaint themselves with their institutes’ referencing style.

The misconception which I held regarding plagiarism was the citing of common knowledge. As duly noted in the coursepack, citing general knowledge is not required (EUCLID 2019, 10). Nonetheless, it can be a cause for concern among undergraduates as many do like to claim that they did not read the information in the text from anywhere. Turabian Writers Guide clarifies this point by noting that citation is required if this common knowledge is “tied to particular researchers” (Turabian 2018, 83). Proper citing should correspond with the style guide of the institution.

3) FIRST-PERSON SINGULAR VERSUS ACADEMIC STYLE

At the undergraduate level, I was discouraging from writing in the first person singular because I am still a novice and will only get to write in the first person at the doctorate level. The justification was that I am not yet producing any new knowledge, but instead, I was consuming knowledge. This “bad advice” of not using first person singular (EUCLID 2019, 16); I found it to constrain free-thinking and critical expression of thoughts. However, I concur that a suitable balance must exist between using the first person singular and academic style (EUCLID 2019). The right balance of the two styles will help present evidence and communicate the author’s critical analysis of such evidence.

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

The coursepack provided several lessons and rules in this section, which challenged what I knew before and even clarified a few confusions regarding the use of punctuations, conjunctions, and parentheses. For instance, before reading the coursepack, I was not confident on where to place the apostrophe after or before “s.” According to the coursepack, an apostrophe should come before the “s” in a singular noun and after “s” in a plural noun to indicate possession (EUCLID 2019, 17). Before engaging with period one reading materials, I left these corrections to Microsoft Word auto-correct and sometimes just left these mistakes unattended.

Another clarification came with the explanation of the use of “its” or “it’s.” I assumed it’s’ was the one that showed possession and not a contraction. The spelling out or writing out of numbers was another area of confusion, which the coursepack explained. I now understand that I should write them as numbers except when they begin a sentence or one or two words (EUCLID 2019). Most of the guidelines for putting together the literature review depend primarily on the writers’ style guide.

5) STYLE GUIDE

Of all the things that indicated to me that academic writing is worth studying and that I was a novice is the various style guides and the different rules. It had never occurred to me that such existed. I only knew of American English and South African English, which I used the most, though not exclusively. I could switch between the two whenever it suited me or if Microsoft Word did not recognize the phrase. However, as I discovered how important it was to stick to one specific style (EUCLID 2019, 24), I desired to learn more and absorb everything. Yet, the realization that I had so much to learn regarding style guides did create an overwhelming feeling. I then remembered a saying that “a journey of a thousand miles begins with one step.”

The coursepack introduced the fact that there are various style guidelines used internationally. Nonetheless, the one used by Euclid University is the Chicago style guide. Furthermore, I learned how to use the Euclid response paper template formatted to meet the Chicago style rules. The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) prescribes which type of English to use, how to format, how to reference, font usage, and so forth. CMS favors American English.

The comparison between American English; and British English was an intriguing revelation. I noted that what is referred to as South African English in Microsoft Word closely resembles British English. The immediate example is the spelling of color, which, in British and South African English, is spelled with a “u.” Though I could not remember being taught which type of English I should use, the period one video has taught me the importance of setting the language preference in Microsoft Word and sticking to it.

The Chicago style recommends that when dealing with regions, we should “capitalize North Africa, West Africa, and East Africa, but not western, eastern, central or southern Africa” (EUCLID 2019, 45). Though I find this suggestion very useful, there is a conflict when it comes to southern Africa. Since South Africa is a country, the south part of Africa is called “Southern Africa.” It raises the question of how do we recognize the south region of Africa without referring to South Africa? The SADC website uses the capitalized version (SADC 2012), which I support to avoid politics of lack of recognition in literature.

Chapter eight (8) of the CMS crib sheet baffled me the quote included at the end of the chapter, which stated:

All health and success does me good, however far off and withdrawn it may appear; all disease and failure helps to make me sad and does me evil, however much sympathy it may have with me or I with it.--Thoreau (EUCLID 2019, 55).

It seemed out of place as it was at the end of the bibliography guide. To understand why it was there, I copied it to Google search. It did open up to the exciting writings of Thoreau; however, it remained unrelated to what I was reading on the CMS.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

This chapter on Latin abbreviations and expressions was a revelation to me as well. It introduced me to the language aspect that I knew little about, though some of the terms included in the chapter were words I have used before ignorantly. Such words as curriculum vitae, versus, pluta paper, and vice versa (EUCLID 2019, 56-58), which I did not associate to Latin. Some of the words and expressions included in the table appeared in law writings, and I never bothered to check what they meant. I have often used the expression ad hoc and curriculum vitae without much thought to their origin, as presented on page 59 of the coursepack. Reading through this chapter created a desire to know more about the origins of words and expressions I read and write.

7) CONCLUSION

I genuinely have come to appreciate the importance of learning academic writing at a doctoral level and how much I need it as there are knowledge gaps in my understanding. As much as I was taught English as a second language throughout my academic life, it had not truly prepared me for writing at a doctoral and international level. As I interacted with the learning materials from period one, I picked up on interesting concepts and knowledge gaps. This paper discussed the conceptions under five headings. In the first heading on plagiarism, I learned that I should cite the original authors properly using the referencing style of Euclid University. I have come to appreciate that I do not have to cite common knowledge. The second concept was first person singular versus academic style. Previous institutions that I attended discouraged using the first person singular, which I have since learned was lousy advice. This response paper is a testament to that freedom. However, there must be a balance between the two styles. The section on the literature review revealed what I learned regarding conjunctions, commas, and so forth. I recognized that a lot of the literature's advice had to do with the style guide I will be using; in this case, it will be the Chicago style. I believe that my knowledge of the Chicago style will continue to grow as I use it throughout my doctoral studies and beyond. The final concept was the Latin abbreviations and expressions. I now have a full appreciation of the origins of certain words and expressions. Indeed, there is much learning and relearning that needs to occur before I refer to myself as an international academician.

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